

EDUCATION SYSTEM UNDER ARYA SAMAJ

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ABSTRACT

The nineteenth century India was an era of revivalism and renaissance where multiple organisations such as Brahma Samaj, Singh Sabha, Dev Samaj, Prarthana Samaj etc. worked towards reformation, development and eradicating social evils from the society. The laying of foundation of Arya Samaj by Dayanand Saraswati in 1875 during this scenario marks a crucial event in the pages of history. The Arya Samaj draw its inspiration from Vedas and indigenous culture. It based itself on the values of equality, karma and merit. It opposed child marriage, purdah system, ban on widow marriage and other evil practices prevailing in the society. Among all the socio-religious reform movements of that time, the "question of women" assumed a crucial place and no other movement was as contributing and successful in imparting education as was the Arya Samaj. Apart from its contribution in education of boys, the paper would focus on the initiatives taken by it in the emancipation of women through the most important pillar in development i.e. education. From the three major dimensions of Arya Samaj- social, religious and educational, our focus would be to study the third one in detail.

KEYWORDS: Arya Samaj, education, women, DAV Colleges, Mahavidyalayas, Gurukulas

INTRODUCTION

Education in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century got divided mainly into two groups- one which supported western education and looked at it as a means of development and modernization and the other which looked back to Indian roots and Vedas for inspiration and supported traditional and indigenous education. While Raja Ram Mohan Roy represented the first group, Swami Dayanand Saraswati led the second group.

Christian missionaries, the flagbearers of Western education propagated knowledge which was incensed with religious zeal and thus trespassed the cultural territory of Hindus. The latter found expression through the new Indian middle class who were searching for an opportunity to meet the missionary challenge¹. The British after colonising India wanted to make servants for employing them in railways, postal services, courts etc. and thus didn't lay any stress on the education of girls as such. The need for educating girls and save the cultural space from the

western ideology found an ideal alternative in Swami Dayanand's ideology and Arya Samaj developed as the most prominent religious movement in North India.²

For better understanding the education system under Arya Samaj, it becomes imperative to equip ourselves with the understanding of ideology of its founder, Dayanand Saraswati. Born in a Brahmin family in Gujarat, Mool Shankar (Dayanand Saraswati) was raised as an orthodox shaivite but he gradually began to be highly inquisitive about the rituals and beliefs particularly after the Shivaratri incident when he saw a mice running on the idol of Lord Shiva. This caused him to question that how couldn't the god save its body from getting polluted by this mice. This is when he began to have reservations about idol worship and the rational on which it was based.³ This search for truth, says Lala Lajpat Rai caused restlessness and he was forced to quit home in 1846. He then became a sanyasi and joined the Saraswati order with the name 'Dayanand'. He met his guru, Swami Virjanand in Mathura in 1860 and studied the Vedas, Sanskrit grammar and various schools of philosophy for three years and then left Mathura with the spirit of reforming contemporary Hinduism.⁴ According to him, truth lay in Vedas which were the supreme authority and Hinduism now was corrupted with superstitions and practices which weren't mentioned in vedas, considering them Anarsha, i.e. false, illegitimate and filled with error.⁵ He laid down his philosophy in his most important text, Satyarth Prakash which was published in 1875, the same year in which Arya Samaj was established.

Indu Bala has discussed the concerns and social ideas of Arya Samaj. Largely concerned with the women question in Arya Samaj like it's support for widow remarriage and its stand against purdah system and the freedom given to women to become its member, Bala also deals with educational doctrines of the organisation which found education to be the solution to all the social abuses. However, the Arya Samaj was not in favor to provide all types of education to women but the minimum which could fulfill their objective to equip them to be ideal wives and mothers not going beyond the prescribed patriarchal framework.

Kaur has studied the education status of women in Punjab in colonial India. There were no honest efforts on the part of colonial government in this field and the little works done were restricted to the male population. Arya Samaj, says Kaur, established more schools for boys

and girls than any other organisation or missionary society. She regards it as the most influential movement for raising the status of women. She has also described shortly the difference in their approach to boys and girls like the minimum age or duration of for completion of schooling and curriculum but Arya Samaj considered education to be the paramount necessity.

SWAMI DAYANAND'S IDEAS ON EDUCATION

Swami Dayanand has elaborately discussed his ideas regarding education in the second and third chapter of Satyarth Prakash. He says "both state and society should make it compulsory upon all to send their children (both male and female) to school after the fifth or eighth year and it should be made a penal offence to keep a child at home after that age". He advocated equal rights for men and women in educational matters. He quoted Manu- "where women led unhappy life, the family is soon destroyed , while that family enjoys perpetual proprietary where women are honoured and lead a joyful existence". According to him, education leads us from darkness to light, from untruth to truth and from ignorance to knowledge. Knowledge is that which gives us the correct and true idea of a thing.⁶ He cited examples of great female scholars from ancient India such as Gargi, Maitreyi, Lopamudra and said that like boys, a girl should acquire sound knowledge and culture by the practice of Brahmacharya and then marry boys of their own choice.⁷ However, he felt that there should be a difference in curriculum of boys'and girls' schools. He first gave priority to grammar, then on phonetics, vedic vocabulary, Sanskrit and philosophy, shastras, medical sciences, geography etc. The curriculum of women's schools included sewing, cooking, music, along with grammar and Vedic shastras, geography etc. Most crucial aim of his education system was religious and moral.

Even before the establishment of Arya Samaj, Dayanand Saraswati established schools based on Vedic system and first Arya School came up in 1868 in Firozepur and Kasganj. He travelled to different parts of India and many branches of Arya Samaj were set up in different cities like Bombay, Lahore, Amritsar, Jalandhar etc. He preached his principles during these tours and which were instrumental in setting up Arya Schools and Colleges. Swami Dayanand died in 1883 after returning from Ajmer.

After his death, the process of formation of schools and development of education grew at a higher pace as his followers saw this as a medium to keep their leader's ideology alive. These schools taught mainly vedic philosophy along with the regular English-oriented curriculum. The Arya Samaj of Lahore played a pivotal role in providing leadership role to the education movement. A trust was established for Dayanand Anglo-Vedic (D.A.V.) and Management Society under the leadership of Lala Lal Chand and an education scheme was drafted for the same.⁸ The first D.A.V. school was established in Lahore in 1886 with Lala Hansraj becoming the first principal and this high-school became a college in 1889 recognised by Punjab University.⁹ A number of schools and colleges were established on its lines. These D.A.V. schools and colleges were a huge success. Now, there started developing differences within the Arya Samaj regarding Dayanand's concept of education. These two groups which emerged were as follows:

- College Party
- Mahatma Party

The D.A.V. group was led by the College Party and the Mahatma Party supported the Gurukul System. The differences were reflected mainly on two issues- the curriculum and the women education. Whereas, the Mahatma Party wanted to inculcate Vedic philosophy, Sanskrit, Granthas based on ancient gurukul tradition and Swami Dayanand's teachings in its curriculum, the College Party wanted the inclusion of English education and government curriculum with more inclination towards professional and economic interests.¹⁰

Coming to the second point of difference, Mahatma Party supported women education but the College Party didn't acknowledge its significance and opposed it (though initially).

A number of institutions like the Arya Schools, Arya Colleges, Ayurvedic Colleges, Sanskrit Schools, primary, middle and high schools and Gurukulas were established throughout North India under its ambit with the maximum being in Punjab followed by United Provinces. The College Party leaders such as Lala Lal Chand and Lala Lajpat Rai were more interested in national politics of INC and social welfare and the Mahatma Party led by Lala Munshi Ram and Devraj were busy in fulfilling their goal of creating a world of Aryanism as was envisioned

by Swami Dayanand. Arya Kanya Pathshala was established in Jalandhar in 1880. A girls' school was opened at Talwan in 1888 by Lala Munshi Ram which was closed due to unworthiness of female teachers. They founded Kanya Mahavidyalaya at Jalandhar in 1896 which was an epoch making move in the history of women education in Modern India and also started supporting education of widows for which hostels were also established. Several Kanya Vidyalayas and Mahavidyalays now were being set up in North India mainly Punjab, Haryana, western United Provinces like the Meerut Kanya Vidyalaya in 1898. In 1889, Kanya Mahavidyalaya started its weekly magazine, 'Panchal Pandita' which propagated ideas in support of female education. Gurukul Kangri was founded in 1902 which became a model for Gurukul System of education.

If we observe the curriculum of D.A.V. Colleges, we would notice that it's an assimilation of East and West regarding which Kenneth W. Jones wrote "English language for adjustment, Hindi for communication with the masses, Sanskrit and works of Dayanand for moral upliftment and science for material progress. Aryas offered answer to the most acute dilemma of occupational mobility and cultural adjustment".¹¹

Female education was on a backfoot due to various reasons at that time- society being conservative, didn't favor it; the colonial government made no honest efforts in this direction and also didn't want to interfere with the traditions and customs of Indian society; lack of trained female teachers etc. Some schools were opened by Christian missionaries for women but the education being provided to students felt like a threat on Hindu traditional sphere and is also considered to be one of the reasons which gave a push to the need of setting up schools for women by the Arya Samaj. One such incident from Lala Munshi Ram's life is evident of this. One day his daughter came running to him and recited a couplet learnt by her at the missionary school-

"Ek bar Isa Isa Bol, Tera kya lagega mol?

Isa mera Ram Ramayya, Isa mera Kishan Kanhaiya"¹²

(Take the name of Jesus once, what will it cost you? Jesus is my Lord Ram, Jesus is my Lord Krishna)

Munshi Ram decided to open schools for girls and alongwith Lala Devraj made drastic efforts in this direction although they faced failures due to lack of funds and lack of enthusiasm on the part of families to send their daughters to schools. Even after many failed attempts, they tried hard in making this successful. The contributions of Lala Devraj and his mother Kahan Devi in this regard who even tried opening a school in their home are commendable. Lala Devraj took a revolutionary step in 1907-08 by introducing English in the curriculum of Kanya Mahavidyalaya and this is when Gurukul Party started to withdraw its support as it opposed anything which wasn't prescribed by Dayanand Saraswati. But it was fortunate that around the same time, especially from the second decade of twentieth century, the College Party started taking women education seriously and Lala Lajpat Rai openly admitted that he regrets opposing it earlier.¹³ This change in ideology was bought mainly by the participation of girls from Kanya Mahavidyalayas in the National Movement. Now, Lala Hansraj (College Party) alongwith Lala Devraj and KMV leaders prepared a scheme for women education in 1919. Thus, both the parties tremendously contributed in the field of education. Arya Samaj was far more successful and had a more momentous impact on the Hindu society than the movements preceding it such as Brahma Samaj, Prathana Samaj, Dev Samaj etc.¹⁴ The number of students rose with each passing year and decade and till today the system of education established by Arya Samaj continues to flourish.

CONCLUSION

Arya Samaj has played a pivotal role in developing the education system on traditional lines and Vedic values. They considered education to be the most important pillar for development of a society and laid stress on equal opportunities for both boys and girls. Dayanand Saraswati's death in 1883 proved rather a catalyst in this field when the party got divided into two groups and both worked in their own ways to take the legacy of their leader forward. There was some difference in curriculum and duration of education for boys and girls which let people see a patriarchal touch in their ideology and becomes a different topic of study but keeping those times in mind, the contribution made by Arya Samaj in setting an education system were tremendous and continues to grow and prosper even today.

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